

MIRREM

Measuring Irregular Migration

www.irregularmigration.eu

Resources on Irregular Migration and Training Materials

*Compilation of training and audiovisual materials for different audiences
with updated data and facts about irregular migration and regularisations*

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Co-funded by:

Canada Excellence
Research Chair in
Migration & Integration

Deliverable Information:

Project Acronym:	Measuring irregular migration and related policies (MIrreM)
Project No.	101061314
WP	WP8 – Impact: stakeholder network and dissemination
Deliverable Type:	Report
Deliverable Name	D8.3 - Compilation of training and audiovisual materials for different audiences with updated data and facts about irregular migration and regularisations
Version:	1
Date:	17/10/2025
Responsible Partner:	Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants (PICUM)
Contributing Partners:	Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants (PICUM), University for Continuing Education Krems (UWK), University of Oxford (OXF), University of Maastricht (UM), University of Potsdam (UP)
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Reviewers:	n.a.
Dissemination Level:	Public

Revision History:

Version	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
1	23/09/2025	Imanol Legarda	PICUM	Initial draft of resources for journalists
1	26/09/2025	Jill Ahrens, Albert Kraller, Michele Levoy	UWK/ PICUM	Co-author feedback resources for journalists
1	26/09/2025	Gianluca Cesaro	PICUM	Respond to feedback and layouting
	26/09/2025	Albert Kraller, Michele Levoy	UWK/PICUM	Final round of review
1	30/09/2025	Gianluca Cesaro	PICUM	Final version resources for journalists
1	17/10/2025	Albert Kraller, Adriana Harm	UWK	Addition of Syllabus MIrreM Spring School, List of Training opportunities for migration scholars and practitioners, addition of abstract
1	21/11/2025	Adriana Harm	UWK	Submitted Version 1

Summary

This document compiles three types of training and information resources: (1) *Resources for journalists: Key findings on irregular migration*, providing both key facts and a directory to further resources, including the two MIRreM handbooks on irregular migration data and regularisation policy, respectively, as well as three short animated videos on the conceptualisation of irregular migration, estimates on irregular migration, and the benefits of regularisation; (2) the *syllabus of the MIRreM Spring School* organised at the University for Continuing Education Krems in March 2025, providing an introduction to irregular migration data organised in 6 thematic sessions (Introduction to basic concepts, data quality, using publicly available data on irregular migration, methods of estimating irregular migration, assessing the impact of policies on irregular migration and the lives of irregular immigrants, and the politics and ethics of numbers; and (3) an overview of Training opportunities for migration scholars and practitioners.

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THE MIRREM PROJECT

MIRREM examines estimates and statistical indicators on the irregular migrant population in Europe as well as related policies, including the regularisation of migrants in irregular situations.

MIRREM analyses policies defining migrant irregularity, stakeholders' data needs and usage, and assesses existing estimates and statistical indicators on irregular migration in the countries under study and at the EU level. Using several coordinated pilots, the project develops new and innovative methods for measuring irregular migration and explores if and how these instruments can be applied in other socio-economic or institutional contexts. Based on a broad mapping of regularisation practices in the EU as well as detailed case studies, MIRREM will develop 'regularisation scenarios' to better understand conditions under which regularisation should be considered as a policy option. Together with expert groups that will be set up on irregular migration data and regularisation, respectively, the project will synthesise findings into a Handbook on data on irregular migration and a Handbook on pathways out of irregularity. The project's research covers 20 countries, including 12 EU countries and the United Kingdom.

TO CITE:

Kraler, A. & Harm, A. (eds) (2025). Resources on irregular migration and training materials. Compilation of training and audiovisual materials for different audiences. Krems: University for Continuing Education (Danube University) Krems. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17675992>

KEYWORDS

Irregular migration; Fact sheet; Guide; Concepts; Estimates; Data; Regularisation; Training material; Syllabus; Training opportunities;

FUNDING ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

In addition, MIRREM benefits from funding provided by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee. The Canadian research component of this project is undertaken, in part, thanks to funding from the Canada Excellence Research Chairs Program of the Government of Canada.

1. RESOURCES FOR JOURNALISTS: KEY FINDINGS ON IRREGULAR MIGRATION

MIRREM

Measuring Irregular Migration

www.irregularmigration.eu

Resources for Journalists: Key Findings on Irregular Migration

Authors: Imanol Legarda Díaz-Aguado, Jill Ahrens, Gianluca Cesaro, Albert Kraler and Michele LeVoy

MIRreM Factsheet, September 2025

Co-funded by:

Canada Excellence
Research Chair in
Migration & Integration

1. DEFINITIONS AND TERMINOLOGY

Who is an irregular migrant?

Who is an irregular migrant?

parents and inherit this precarious residence status.

Watch our [animation](#).

Irregular migrants are people whose residence is not recognised by the country they live in. They are unable to obtain a residence permit or citizenship because of restrictive migration and residence policies. Many have had residence permissions linked to employment, study, family, or international protection, but those permits were either temporary or very precarious and their validity expired. There are also children who are born to undocumented

Notes on how to talk about irregular migration

- **Use accurate and respectful language:** Say *undocumented* or *irregular*, not *illegal*; avoid militaristic terms like *invasion* or terms used for natural disasters like *flood*.
 - **Centre migrants' voices:** Let people tell their own stories, not only governments, law enforcement or officials.
 - **Provide context:** Explain structural drivers of migration, as well as how laws and policies create situations of 'irregularity'.
 - **Acknowledge residence permit precarity:** People often lose their residence status for reasons beyond their control, such as administrative barriers, restrictive policies, or changes in employment.
 - **Avoid stereotypes and sensationalism:** Do not frame migration solely in terms of crime, security or crisis.
 - **Choose imagery carefully:** Use visuals that reflect dignity and humanity, rather than spectacle or dehumanisation.
 - **Protect privacy and safety:** Do not expose individuals or groups to risks of stigmatisation, retaliation, or legal consequences.
-

- **Highlight contributions:** Show social, cultural, civic and economic roles of migrants.
- **Include local perspectives:** Show both migrants' everyday realities and the responses of host communities, avoiding polarising 'us vs. them' framings.
- **Consider intersectionality:** Recognise how gender, age, race, class, or sexuality shape the lived experiences of migrants.

For more on terms and definitions, see: Chapter 2: What is irregular migration? by Albert Kraller, Tuba Birca and Ann Singleton in the [Handbook on Irregular Migration Data](#) (MirreM 2025)

Resources on the role of disinformation, discourse construction, media impact on migration and effective framing strategies:

Disinformation and media framing shape perceptions of irregular migration, highlighting the need for accurate, responsible reporting. Various stakeholders – including journalists, policymakers, academics and civil society actors – play a role in shaping and responding to these narratives.

Chapter 4 on Stakeholders by Imanol Legarda in the [Handbook on Regularisation Policies](#) (MirreM 2025)

2. MEASURING IRREGULAR MIGRATION

Estimates

What is an estimate: Available data on irregular migration is limited, fragmented and methodologically diverse. Therefore, the most reliable approach is to produce an ‘estimate’, expressed as a minimum and a maximum range, rather than a precise figure. The MirreM research project compiles various existing estimates and evaluates their quality to get a clearer picture of the number of irregular migrants residing in the 20 countries in Europe, North Africa and North America covered by the project.

For further reading on data literacy, see: [Towards the More Effective Use of Irregular Migration Data in Policymaking](#), by Jasmijn Slootjes and Ravenna Sohst (MirreM, 2024)

How to measure the irregular migrant population

Check the [handbook on irregular migration data](#) for more on measurement and practices, including pilot methodologies.

Watch our [animation](#).

The irregular migrant population in Europe has remained stable in recent decades

- Between 2016 and 2023, 2.6 to 3.2 million irregular migrants are estimated to have been living in the 12 European countries (including the UK) covered by the MirreM project.
- Estimates across these European countries put the share of irregular migrants at less than 1% of the total population
- Overall, the [MirreM Working Paper The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe](#) suggests no definitive change in the number and share of the irregular migrant population in Europe since 2008 – contrary to a public narrative of a continuous rise of irregular migration.

Check the [press release](#) on the launch of the MirreM database for further information.

Data portal on irregular migration stocks

The [interactive map](#) below presents the **most recent irregular migration population estimates** of at least medium quality in different countries since 2008. These estimates were compiled and their quality was assessed as part of the MirreM project. Where available, these estimates are displayed alongside Clandestino project benchmark estimates from 2008. Individual country pages containing all estimates compiled by the MirreM project, including top line findings and links to related publications.

The MirreM Public Data Portal on Irregular Migration Stocks

Hover and click on the countries and other objects below to explore the data

3. REGULARISATION POLICIES

Regularising the status of irregular migrants has benefits that extend beyond the individuals concerned. For migrants, it provides security of residence, access to rights, and opportunities to participate fully in society.

For host communities, regularisation reduces labour market exploitation, increases tax and social security contributions, and supports fair competition for employers. It also improves public health and safety by ensuring that all residents can access services and are not forced into precarious or informal arrangements.

At the societal level, regularisation strengthens social cohesion and integration, while giving governments better oversight and governance of migration. Far from being a one-sided measure, regularisation creates mutual gains for migrants, economies, and communities alike.

[Regularisations in Europe and North America: Comparative Reflections on Societal Challenges and Benefits](#) by Maristella Cacciapaglia et al. (MIRreM 2025)

Why regularisation benefits everyone

Check the [handbook](#) on regularisation policies for practices, debates and outcomes.

Watch our [animation](#)

There is no evidence for a 'pull effect' of regularisation policies

Opponents of regularisation policies often refer to a potential 'pull effect', arguing that regularisation policies may encourage further irregular migration. However, case studies in Southern Europe and the United States suggest that migration flows are shaped primarily by economic conditions and social networks, rather than by the availability of regularisation policies.

[Working Paper on Migration Responses to \(Non-\) Enforcement](#) by Mathias Czaika, Jiancheng Gu, Albert Kraler and Lydia Rössl (FAiR, 2024)

Chapter 8: Regularisation in today's political context by Imanol Legarda in the [Handbook on Regularisation Policies](#) (MIrreM, 2025)

Impacts and outcomes

Regularisation has demonstrable social, economic, legal and political impacts, but outcomes depend on policy design and wider framework of migration governance. We distinguish between ongoing regularisation mechanisms and time-limited regularisation programmes.

- Insecure, conditional or employer-dependent residence statuses can limit the effectiveness and durability of regularisation measures.
- Both intended and unintended consequences should be systematically monitored – including effects on labour markets, the protection of migrant rights, and long-term integration trajectories – and regularisation policies should be adapted accordingly.
- Regularisation policies operate within broader political, social, and international contexts, which shape both their feasibility and their outcomes.

Time-limited regularisation programmes demonstrate how rapid responses can prevent irregularity, but they carry risks when they are short-term or there are no pathways towards durable residence permits.

4. RETURNS

Using the return rate to measure effectiveness of return policy is deeply flawed and creates an unwarranted pressure for restrictions

The claim that only 20% of return decisions are implemented is widespread in political discourse at the [EU](#) and [national](#) level. But calculating the return rate as the ratio between return decisions and confirmed returns in a given year is deeply flawed and potentially misleading:

Issues with counting return decisions:

- Statistics on return decisions also include cases where migrants hold a residence status in another Member State, or are able to obtain a residence status and are transferred ('readmitted') under EU rules such as the Dublin III Regulation to another Member State. According to a European Parliament briefing, this accounts for approximately 20% of cases.
- In some Member States, an individual migrant may receive multiple return decisions if apprehended several times in the same year, according to the same EP briefing.
- In certain Member States, return decisions may also be issued to asylum applicants while their procedure is still ongoing.
- A considerable number of return decisions are not enforceable, either because they are issued only pro-forma as a formal step without an intention of execution, or because their enforcement is (temporarily) suspended (e.g. *Duldung* in Germany).
- When aggregated at the EU level, statistics may double-count individuals who have been issued multiple return decisions in multiple Member States.

Issues with counting returns carried out:

- There is no systematic EU-wide recording of how many mandatory returns are carried out following the issuance of a 'return decision' (obligation to leave the territory).
- The number of 'effective returns' in a given year often includes return decisions issued in previous years, not solely the current year.
- Migrants may also opt to return by themselves without reporting this to the authorities.

[EU Policy Framework on irregular migrants](#) by Martin Wagner, Alan Desmond and Albert Kraler (MlrreM 2024)

Video: [Who is an irregular migrant?](#) (MlrreM 2025)

[Measuring irregular migration and returns in the EU](#) by Costica Dumbrava (European Parliament Think Tank 2025)

The return of irregular migrants ordered to leave mainly happens within the first two years after a return decision

Enforcement of return and regularisation are often understood as opposite options. In reality, however, these two pathways out of irregularity happen at different times. A recent German study shows that the likelihood of resolving irregular status is highest within the first two years after the obligation to leave becomes enforceable. After this period, the likelihood of voluntary departure remains almost stable, only increasing minimally and leaving regularisation as the only viable pathway out of irregularity.

[Return or regularization? A temporal analysis of rejected asylum seekers in Germany](#) by Laura Peitz (EUI Working Paper 2025)

5. UNDERSTANDING MIGRATION GOVERNANCE

The MirreM Final Conference brought together leading international migration researchers, EU policy-makers, representatives of national administrations and civil society to discuss key findings about irregular migration and regularisation policies.

Click on the links below to watch the panel discussions.

[PANEL 1: Measuring irregular migration](#)

How many migrants are living without regular status?

What are the current data gaps?

Which innovative methodologies are emerging?

Chair: Tuba Bircan, Professor, Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Speakers:

- Alejandra Rodríguez Sánchez, Postdoctoral Research Scholar, University of Potsdam
- Fabian Bach, Team Leader, Eurostat
- Amparo González Ferrer, Deputy Director General of the Reception System at the Secretary of State for Migration, Spain
- Ann Singleton, Reader in Migration Policy, University of Bristol, and external advisor to IOM's Global Migration Data Analysis Centre

PANEL 2: Policy responses to irregular migration

What are examples of promising practices towards individuals remaining in the country despite return orders?

Which trends are emerging in the current political climate?

How can fundamental rights be properly safeguarded within a return-focused approach?

Chair: Anna Triandafyllidou, Professor, Canada Excellence Research Chair in Migration and Integration, Toronto Metropolitan University

Speakers:

- Maegan Hendow, Senior Researcher, International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD)
- Blanca Garcés Mascareñas, Senior Research Fellow, Barcelona Centre for International Affairs (CIDOB)
- Mauro Gagliardi, Cabinet of European Commissioner for Internal Affairs and Migration Magnus Brunner

PANEL 3: The impact of regularisation policies

Is there any evidence of a so-called “pull effect”?

Can regularisation be a more effective alternative to return?

How can countries benefit from regularisation policies and programs – economically and socially?

Chair: Laetitia Van der Vennet, Senior Advocacy Officer for Children, Family and Youth and Regularisation, PICUM

Speakers:

- Albert Kraler, Assistant Professor and MirreM Project Leader, Department for Migration and Globalisation, Universität für Weiterbildung Krems
- Ana Damas de Matos, Economist, International Migration Division, Directorate for Employment, Labour and Social Affairs, OECD
- Laura Peitz, Researcher German Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF)
- Brigitte Gremaud, Centre de Contact Suisses-Immigrés (CCSI), Switzerland
- Rosita Fibbi, Centre de Contact Suisses-Immigrés (CCSI), Switzerland

MIRREM PUBLICATIONS AND RESOURCES

Below is a selection of key resources produced by MirreM researchers throughout the duration of the project.

Handbooks:

- [Handbook on Irregular Migration Data: Concepts, Methods and Practices](#)
- [Handbook on Regularisation Policies: Practices, Debates and Outcomes](#)

Researching irregular migration:

- [Conceptualising migrant irregularity for measurement purposes](#)

Estimates of irregular migration:

- [Local-level indicators and estimates](#)
- [Public database on irregular migration flow estimates and indicators](#)
- [Public database on irregular migration stock estimates](#) ([press release](#) + [data portal](#))

Methods to estimate irregular migration

- [Review of traditional and innovative methods](#)
- [Mortality data](#)
- [Air passenger data](#)
- [Social media surveys](#)
- [Machine learning](#)
- [GP registrations \(UK\)](#)
- [Labour force surveys \(Türkiye, UK\)](#)

Policy frameworks on irregular migration:

- [National Laws and Policies](#)
- [Local Level Laws and Policies](#)
- [EU Policy Framework](#)

Country case studies:

- [Belgium](#)
 - [Bosnia and Herzegovina](#)
 - [Canada](#)
 - [Finland](#)
 - [France](#)
 - [Germany](#)
 - [Greece](#)
 - [Ireland](#)
-

- [Italy](#)
- [Morocco](#)
- [Netherlands](#)
- [Poland](#)
- [Portugal](#)
- [Serbia](#)
- [Spain](#)
- [Tunisia](#)
- [Türkiye](#)
- [UK](#)
- [USA](#)

Comparative analysis of regularisation policies:

- [Regularisations in Europe and North America: Comparative Reflections on Societal Challenges and Benefits](#)

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2. MIrreM SPRING SCHOOL: SYLLABUS AND SUGGESTED READINGS

Albert Kraler, Denis Kierans, Arjen Leerkes, Alejandra Rodriguez Sanchez & Lalaine Siruno

INTRODUCTION

From March 19 to 21, 2025, the University for Continuing Education (Danube University) Krems hosted the MIrreM Spring School, an intensive training programme designed for researchers and professionals working on irregular migration, following the IMISCOE Spring Conference on “[The Regularity of irregularity: Rethinking migration paradigms](#)”, which participants of the training school were encouraged to participate. Organised by the MIrreM team at the Department for Migration and Globalisation in collaboration with key MIrreM partners involved in assessing the quantitative dimension of migrant irregularity, the event brought together participants from across Europe, North Africa, the Middle East and North America to explore the quantitative dimensions of migrant irregularity.

Over the course of two and a half days, attendees engaged in hands-on workshops and expert-led lectures that covered statistical indicators, estimation methods, conceptual frameworks for measuring irregular migrant populations as well as ethical and political aspects of quantifying migrant irregularity.

Sessions focused on practical tools for interpreting available data, estimating population sizes, and analysing the living and working conditions of migrants with irregular status. In addition to technical training, the programme facilitated in-depth discussions between participants involving both early career stage researchers and practitioners working at national institutions, civil society organisations and international organisations on different aspects of conceptualising, quantifying and disseminating information on irregular migration, fostering a collaborative environment for knowledge exchange.

The following syllabus provides an overview of the training programme of the two and a half days. It offers a model how a short intensive training on irregular migration data – or indeed related topics – can be implemented and hopefully serves as an inspiration and useful resource for university teachers as well as trainers working with practitioners.

Further course materials (e.g. lecture slides) can be obtained upon request at info@irregularmigration.eu or from individual trainers involved in the programme.

We recommend using the *Handbook on irregular migration data. Concepts, methods and practices* (Kierans & Kraler, 2025) as key resource for a training.

Denis Kierans & Albert Kraler (eds.). *Handbook on Irregular Migration Data. Concepts, Methods and Practices*. Krems: University of Krems Press, 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.48341/g31s-vq79>

SYLLABUS

Session 1: Introduction to Basic Concepts: What is Irregular Migration? Who Belongs to the Population of Irregular Migrants? What are Stocks and Flows?	
Session Instructor(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Albert Kraler (University for Continuing Education - Danube University Krems)
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Be familiar with different conceptualisations of migrant irregularity, their scope and various dimensions of irregularity Understand the different epistemological, disciplinary and methodological foundations of different conceptual approaches (legal vs. sociological perspectives; static vs. dynamic perspectives, etc.) Be able to apply different perspectives in analysing irregular migration
Session description	<p>This session introduces key definitions and related conceptualisations of irregular migration, in part drawing on participants' pre-participation essays.</p> <p>We will begin by clarifying fundamental legal and demographic terms (e.g. migrants, stocks, flows, foreign nationals) and identifying core analytical dimensions that shape understanding of migrant irregularity. These include national jurisdictions, individual's legal attachment to different legal orders, and distinctions between movement and residence, etc.</p> <p>Using a mapping of terminology, we will explore how different terms used to describe migrants in an irregular situation (and related populations) carry distinct, connotations, geographies and underlying assumptions. This will provide a foundation for examining how different conceptualisations of migrant irregularity are constructed and how they are shaped by various epistemological and disciplinary perspectives.</p> <p>Finally, we will discuss the role of migration law in structuring legal status positions and a related hierarchy of rights, by using the lens of 'civic stratification'.</p>
Format	This session will be based on an interactive discussion, involving short instructor-led inputs, plenary discussions, and short, small group work to encourage critical engagement with key concepts.
Key reading	Kraler, A., & Ahrens, J. (2023). Conceptualising Migrant Irregularity for Measurement Purposes. In M ^{Irre} M Working Paper No. 2 (Version 3). Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7868237
Suggested additional readings and resources	Ambrosini, M. (2016), From "illegality" to Tolerance and Beyond: Irregular Immigration as a Selective and Dynamic Process. <i>International Migration</i> , 54(1), 144-159 https://doi.org/10.1111/imig.12214

	<p>Chauvin, S., and Garcés-Mascreñas, B. (2012). Beyond Informal Citizenship: The New Moral Economy of Migrant Illegality. <i>International Political Sociology</i> 6(3): 241–59. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-5687.2012.00162.x</p> <p>De Genova, N. P. (2002). Migrant ‘Illegality’ and Deportability in Everyday Life. <i>Annual Review of Anthropology</i> 31(1): 419–47. https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.anthro.31.040402.085432</p> <p>European Commission. Directorate General for Home Affairs and European Migration Network. (2024). <i>Asylum and Migration Glossary</i> https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary_en (online resource only)</p> <p>Hinterberger, K. F. (2023). <i>Regularisations of Irregularly Staying Migrants in the EU. A Comparative Legal Analysis of Austria, Germany and Spain</i>. Vienna: Nomos https://doi.org/10.5771/9783748912798, pp. 59-46</p> <p>Jasso, G., Massey, D. S., Rosenzweig, M. R., & Smith, J. P. (2008). From Illegal to Legal: Estimating Previous Illegal Experience among New Legal Immigrants to the United States. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 42(4), 803-843. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-7379.2008.00148.x</p> <p>Sironi, A., Bauloz, C., and Emmanuel, M.. (2019). Glossary on Migration. International Organization of Migration. https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/iml_34_glossary.pdf</p>
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Session 2: What is 'Good' Data? Validity, Reliability, and FAIR Data Principles in the Context of Irregular Migration Data.

Session Instructor(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lalaine Siruno (United Nations University-MERIT/ Maastricht University) • Arjen Leerkes (Maastricht University/ Erasmus University Rotterdam)
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the concepts of data validity (accuracy) and reliability (consistency) and their importance in migration research • Be familiar with the FAIR data principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and how statistical agencies like Eurostat apply them • Recognise the challenges in ensuring high-quality data in the context of irregular migration, where data gaps and measurement difficulties are common
Session description	<p>This session provides foundational knowledge for the following workshop on utilising publicly available data on irregular migration.</p> <p>We will explore key considerations when assessing the quality of irregular migration data, focusing on validity and reliability. The session will introduce the FAIR data principles and examine how organisations like Eurostat apply them in practice. To ground these concepts in real-world applications, we will</p>

	analyse case studies from the MIrreM and FAiR projects and other relevant research initiatives.
Format	This interactive session will be a combination of a teacher-led lecture and a short small group discussion, where participants will analyse real-world data examples and reflect on the challenges of ensuring validity and reliability in irregular migration statistics.
Key readings	<p>Babbie, E. R. (2021). <i>The Practice of Social Research</i> (15th ed.). Cengage Learning Inc. [especially Chapter 5]</p> <p>Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., . . . Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship. <i>Scientific Data</i>, 3(1), 160018. https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18</p>
Suggested additional readings and resources	<p>Achermann, C. (2009). Multi-perspective research on foreigners in prisons in Switzerland. In I. van Liempt & V. Bilger (Eds.), <i>Ethics of Migration Research Methodology: Dealing with Vulnerable Immigrants</i> (pp. 42-80). Sussex Academic Press.</p> <p>Eurostat. (2021). European Statistical System (ESS) Handbook for Quality and Metadata Reports. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-manuals-and-guidelines/-/ks-gq-21-021</p> <p>Eurostat. (2024). Enforcement of immigration legislation statistics.</p> <p>Leerkes, A., Van Os, R., & Boersema, E. (2017). What drives ‘soft deportation’? Understanding the rise in Assisted Voluntary Return among rejected asylum seekers in the Netherlands. <i>Population, Space and Place</i>, 23(8), e2059. https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2059</p> <p>Massey, D. S., & Capoferro, C. (2004). Measuring undocumented migration. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 38(3), 1075-1102. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-7379.2004.tb00229.x</p> <p>Sinnige, M., Cleton, L., & Leerkes, A. (2025). Determinants of Enforced Return: A Quantitative Analysis of the Spectrum of (In) voluntariness Among Rejected Asylum Seekers in the Netherlands. <i>Population, Space and Place</i>, 31(2), e2886. https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2886</p> <p>Staring, R. (2009). Different methods to research irregular migration. In I. van Liempt & V. Bilger (Eds.), <i>Ethics of Migration Research Methodology: Dealing with Vulnerable Immigrants</i> (pp. 83-97). Sussex Academic Press.</p>

	Taylor, L. (2017). What is data justice? The case for connecting digital rights and freedoms globally. <i>Big Data & Society</i> , 4(2). https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951717736335
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Sessions 3&4: Workshop – Using Publicly Available Data on Irregular Migration to Describe Irregular Migration

Session Instructor(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Denis Kierans (University of Oxford), • Arjen Leerkes (University of Maastricht/Erasmus University Rotterdam) • Lalaine Siruno (University of Maastricht)
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be familiar with some of the latest research on irregular migration stocks and flows • Understand the strengths and limitations of irregular migration data • Be able to apply the M_{Irre}M quality assessment criteria to irregular migration data • Critically assess and contextualise the use of irregular migration data in various settings.
Session description	<p>In this workshop, we will discuss the findings from the M_{Irre}M project work in relation to estimates and indicators of irregular migration stocks and flows. We will cover the compilation and evaluation of estimates and indicators, as well as the broader findings of the research and some of its impacts. However, the bulk of the session will be dedicated to hands-on group work, focussed on participants’ learning how to interrogate the quality of irregular migration estimates and reflect these details when they use the data.</p> <p>The session will begin with presentations by the instructors, covering:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M_{Irre}M quality assessment criteria for irregular migration stocks and flows • Demonstrate how to assess irregular migration data, using specific country-level examples • Cross-country insights into the quality of irregular migration data and trends across countries. • Broader impacts and policy implications of the research <p>Following the presentation, the participants will then be divided into smaller groups, to apply the M_{Irre}M quality criteria to asses irregular migration data. The composition of the groups will be pre-determined by the instructors, to ensure diversity in background/training and current roles/affiliations. Using the pre-participation essay (country context document), or other relevant resource, the groups will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyse the quality of selected irregular migration dataset. • Develop a narrative that accounts for the irregular migration data strengths, limitations and biases. • Guiding questions will prompt participants to reflect on how these data are used in policymaking, media reporting, and otherwise circulate in public discourse.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants will also be prompted to reflect on their use of irregular migration data in their own work and exchange insights and practice. <p>Each group will present their findings in the plenary, highlighting key takeaways. The session will conclude with a synthesis of insights, including an inventory of good practices and potential pitfalls when using publicly available data on irregular migration.</p>
<p>Format</p>	<p>This session will follow an interactive workshop format, consisting of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A short introductory presentation by the instructors Group work with structured analysis and discussion, Group presentations in a plenary session, A wrap-up discussion to consolidate key findings.
<p>Key readings</p>	<p>Kierans, D., & Vargas-Silva, C. (2024) The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe. MIrreM Working Paper No. 11 (Version 1). Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13857073</p> <p>Siruno, L., Leerkes, A., Hendow, M., & Brunovská, E. (2024) MIrreM Working Paper on Irregular Migration Flows. In MIrreM Working Paper No. 9. Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10702228</p>
<p>Suggested additional readings and resources</p>	<p>Boswell, C. (2009). Knowledge, Legitimation and the Politics of Risk: The Functions of Research in Public Debates on Migration, <i>Political Studies</i>, 57(1), 165-186. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9248.2008.00729.x</p> <p>Vespe, M., Natale, C. and Pappalardo, L. (2017). Data sets on irregular migration and irregular migrants in the European Union, <i>Migration Policy Practice</i>, 7(2), 29-33. https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/migration_policy_practice_journal_30.pdf</p> <p>Vollmer, B. A. (2011). Policy Discourses on Irregular Migration in the EU- ‘Number Games’ and ‘Political Games’. <i>European Journal of Migration and Law</i>, 13(3), 317-339. https://doi.org/10.1163/157181611X587874</p> <p>Savatic, F., Thiollet, H., Mesnard, A., Senne, J.-N., & Jaulin, T. (2024). Borders Start with Numbers: How Migration Data Create ‘Fake Illegals’. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 1-32. https://doi.org/10.1177/01979183231222169</p> <p><u>Media coverage (sample):</u></p> <p>Dampier, G. (2025) “Enough learnt helplessness. Here’s how Britain ends illegal migration” in The Telegraph, 24 January 2025. https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2025/01/24/enough-learned-helplessness-britain-end-illegal-migration/</p> <p>Hymas, C. (2024) “Britain has most illegal migrants in Europe, study finds” in The Telegraph, 7 October 2024.</p>

	<p>https://www.telegraph.co.uk/politics/2024/10/07/britain-has-most-illegal-migrants-in-europe-study-finds/</p> <p>Tahir, T. (2024) “Evidence shows far-right claims on illegal migrants are 'hyperbolic'” in The National, 7 October 2024. https://www.thenationalnews.com/news/europe/2024/10/07/static-illegal-migrant-numbers-undermine-hyperbolic-far-right-campaigns-in-europe/</p> <p>Taylor, D. (2024) “Irregular migration into UK and large European countries is same as 2008, research shows” in The Guardian, 7 October 2024.</p>
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Sessions 5: Methods for Estimating Irregular Migration

Session Instructor(s)	Alejandra Rodríguez Sánchez (University of Potsdam)
Learning outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain insight into the primary traditional methods employed for estimating irregular migration. • Critically evaluate the limitations and challenges associated with these conventional approaches. • Comprehend the objectives and advancements offered by innovative estimation techniques. • Acquire hands-on experience with traditional estimation methods through the application of simulated data.
Session description	<p>This workshop introduces participants to methodologies used in estimating irregular migration, highlighting their assumptions, limitations, and potential biases. The session begins with an overview of why estimating irregular migration is crucial, considering its dual-use problem (research and policy) and ethical dimensions. It then covers common estimation methods, including survey-based approaches, demographic models, and statistical techniques such as multiple systems estimation and residual methods.</p> <p>Using real-world case studies, including the PEW Research Center's approach and examples from Japan, the U.S., and Australia, participants will explore the application of these methods across different contexts.</p> <p>In the second part of the session, participants will engage in a practical exercise using simulated data. Working in groups, they will attempt to replicate one of the discussed methods using R, allowing them to apply theoretical concepts in practice. The session concludes with a discussion on innovative approaches, including alternative data sources such as rice consumption, flight data, and biometric records, as well as potential methodological advancements in irregular migration estimation.</p> <p>Session Structure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction: Why is estimating irregular migration important? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The dual-use problem (research and policymaking) b. Ethical considerations

	<p>2. Common methods for estimating irregular migration stocks and flows</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Survey-based approaches b. Demographic methods c. Multiple systems estimation d. Residual methods <p>3. Case Studies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. PEW Research Center's approach in different countries b. Estimation examples from Japan, the U.S., and Australia <p>4. Practical Exercise:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Using simulated data to replicate one of the estimation methods in R <p>5. Innovative Approaches to Estimating Irregular Migration</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Improving traditional methods b. Exploring new data sources: Rice consumption, flight data, biometric data (Example: SAR data for border monitoring) c. Developing new methodological approaches <p>6. Conclusion & Key Takeaways</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Summary of key methods and their limitations b. Reflection on ethical considerations and data gaps c. Future directions in irregular migration research
Format	<p>This session will follow the following format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short lecture introducing key concepts and methodologies • Case study discussions • Hands-on data exercise in R • Group work and discussion
Key readings	<p>Rodríguez Sánchez, A., & Tjaden, J. (2023). <i>Estimating Irregular Migration – A Review of Traditional and Innovative Methods</i>. MIRreM Working Paper No. 4 (Version 2). Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8380854</p>
Suggested additional readings and resources	<p>Jandl, M. (2011). Methods, approaches and data sources for estimating stocks of irregular migrants. <i>International Migration</i>, 49(5), 53-77. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2435.2011.00701.x</p> <p>Van Hook, J., Morse, A., Capps, R., & Gelatt, J. (2021). <i>Uncertainty about the Size of the Unauthorized Foreign-Born Population in the United States</i>. <i>Demography</i>, 58(6), 2315-2336. https://doi.org/10.1215/00703370-9491801</p> <p>Nixon, S. (2022). Of Rice and Men: Rice Consumption-Based Estimates of Undocumented Persons in Malaysia. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 019791832211264. https://doi.org/10.1177/01979183221126466</p> <p>Taylor, D. (2024) “Irregular migration into UK and large European countries is same as 2008, research shows” in <i>The Guardian</i>, 7 October 2024.</p>

Session 6: Policy impacts on irregular migration and the lives of irregular migrants	
Session Instructor(s)	Alejandra Rodríguez Sánchez (University of Potsdam)
Learning outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critically evaluate the framing of policy claims related to irregular migration as presented in the literature • Identify and explain the challenges in identifying and estimating policy effects • Explain different methodological approaches used to assess policy impacts
Session description	<p>Migration policy is currently one of the most salient issues in political debates and the media. Yet their impact is difficult to assess. In this workshop, students will learn the basic framework for the evaluation of policies aimed at controlling or reducing migration, with a special focus on irregular migration. We will discuss the different type of policies (or policy messages) often enacted with the purpose of changing the incentives of migrants. We will look at the methods used in the literature to estimate these effects, the data available, and the pitfalls or challenges of empirical studies. We will engage in a hypothetical study aimed at identifying the impact of a change in policy in the probability of overstaying. The study of policy impacts on irregular migration is riddled with substantial challenges.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Types of policies 2. Features of policies <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Sequential b. Random (variation in time or space) c. Differences across countries d. Micro and Macro studies 3. Causal Inference for evaluating policy impacts <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Challenges for micro studies (selection bias) b. Challenges for macro studies 4. Case studies <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. US-Mexico b. Australia c. Central Mediterranean 5. Exercise: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Hypothetical evaluation: What are the effects of policies A, B, and C on overstaying your visa? 6. Conclusions
Format	This session will be based on an interactive discussion, involving short inputs by the session instructor, plenary discussions, and short group work
Key reading	Rodríguez Sánchez, A., Wucherpfennig, J., Rischke, R., & Iacus, S. M. (2023). Search-and-rescue in the Central Mediterranean Route does not induce

	<p>migration: Predictive modeling to answer causal queries in migration research. <i>Scientific Reports</i>, 13(1), 11014. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-38119-4</p>
Suggested additional readings and resources	<p>Czaika, M., & De Haas, H. (2016). <i>The Effect of Visas on Migration Processes</i>. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 50(3), 626-657. https://heindehaas.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/the-effect-of-visas-on-migration-on-migration-processes-2017.pdf</p> <p>Massey, D. S., & Pren, K. A. (2012). Unintended consequences of US immigration policy: Explaining the post-1965 surge from Latin America. <i>Population and development review</i>, 38(1), 1-29. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2012.00470.x</p> <p>McKenzie, D., & Yang, D. (2024). Field and natural experiments in migration. In <i>Handbook of Research Methods in Migration</i> (pp. 48-82). Edward Elgar Publishing. https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/bd17d3b9-8d7c-5340-99b4-bc1d2b88875b/content</p>

Session 7: The Politics and Ethics of Numbers

Session Instructor(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arjen Leerkes (Maastricht University/Erasmus University Rotterdam) • Albert Kraler (University for Continuing Education - Danube University Krems)
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this session participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critically assess ethical challenges in irregular migration research • Analyse the political dynamics influencing migration research • Interrogate the impact of migration statistics on policy and public discourse • Develop strategies for ethical research design and dissemination • Enhance responsible engagement with policy and public debates
Session description	<p>This session explores the ethical and political challenges of researching irregular migration, emphasising the risks of misuse and politicisation of research findings. Drawing on ethical guidelines from the European Sociological Association and Dutch universities, the session will address concerns around research integrity, informed consent, and mitigating vulnerabilities.</p> <p>Using insights from Horizon Europe projects on return policies and irregular migration measurement, participants will examine the ethical dilemmas researchers face, including the balance between academic freedom and policy engagement. The session will also apply Burawoy’s (2005) typology of sociology—professional, policy, public, and critical—to demonstrate the legitimate role of social science in migration research.</p>

	A key focus will be on strategies to navigate ethical dilemmas, including fostering ongoing ethical reflection, ensuring balanced research design, engaging diverse stakeholders, and promoting transparency. The session will critically reflect on the risks of publication bias and the responsibilities of researchers when their work enters public and policy debates.
Format	The session will consist of a mix of a lecture type and interactive formats. A brief double lecture on the different roles of scientific research in policy making and ethical challenges arising from these different roles will introduce and frame the session. In the second part of the session, we invite participants to reflect on ethical challenges encountered in research they have or are conducting and their ways to address these.
Key reading	Cyrus, N. (2023). Ethical Benchmarking for the Measurement of Irregular Migration. In MIRreM Policy Brief No.1. Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042022
Suggested additional readings and resources	<p>Burawoy, M. (2005). For public sociology. <i>American sociological review</i>, 70(1), 4-28. https://doi.org/10.1177/000312240507000102</p> <p>Bauböck, R., Mourão Permoser, J., & Ruhs, M. (2022). The ethics of migration policy dilemmas. <i>Migration Studies</i>, 10(3), 427-441. https://doi.org/10.1093/migration/mnac029</p> <p>Cyrus, N. (2023). Ethical Benchmarking in Irregular Migration Research. In MIRreM Working Paper No.3. Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8389189</p> <p>Düvell, F., Triandafyllidou, A., & Vollmer, B. (2010). Ethical issues in irregular migration research in Europe. <i>Population, Space and Place</i>, 16(3), 227-239. https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.590</p> <p>van Liempt, I., Bilger, V. (2018). Methodological and Ethical Dilemmas in Research Among Smuggled Migrants. In: Zapata-Barrero, R., Yalaz, E. (eds) <i>Qualitative Research in European Migration Studies</i>. IMISCOE Research Series. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-76861-8_15</p>

3. TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES IN MIGRATION

Jill Ahrens

In recent years, the landscape of academic and professional training in migration studies has expanded significantly, offering a diverse array of opportunities for scholars and practitioners to deepen their expertise. From winter and summer schools hosted by leading institutions such as the European University Institute in Florence and the University of Oxford, to specialized programs like the MiReKoc Summer School in Istanbul and the Odysseus Summer School on EU Immigration and Asylum Law in Brussels, these initiatives provide intensive, interdisciplinary learning environments. Covering themes from migration economics and human rights to applied research methods with marginalized populations, these training opportunities reflect the growing complexity and relevance of migration research in today's global context.

3.1 ANNUAL TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES IN MIGRATION

Migration Winter Academy

Organisation: European University Institute

Location: Florence, Italy

Month: February

Website: <https://migrationpolicycentre.eu/training/>

Migration Summer School

Organisation: Migration Policy Centre, European University Institute

Location: Florence, Italy

Month: July

Website: <https://migrationpolicycentre.eu/migration-summer-school/>

IMISCOE PhD Winter & Summer Schools

Organisation: IMISCOE (International Migration Research Network)

Location: Different European cities

Month: July and other months

Website: <https://www.imiscoe.org/training-phds/phd-winter-and-summer-schools>

MiReKoc Summer School

Organisation: MiReKoc

Location: Istanbul, Turkey

Month: July

Website: <https://miss.ku.edu.tr/summer-school/>

Migration Summer School

Organisation: University of York & University of Sheffield

Location: Thessaloniki, Greece

Month: July

Website: <https://york.citycollege.eu/frontend/articles.php?cid=394&t=Summer-Schools>

Summer School on Migration Studies

Organisation: Geographic Migration Centre ([GEOMIGRACE](#)), Dep. of Social Geography and Regional Development, Charles University in cooperation with International Organisation for Migration, Country Office Czech Republic

Location: Prague, Czechia

Month: August/September

Websites: <http://geomigrace.cz/en/?s=summer+school> and <https://czechia.iom.int/migration-on-studies>

3.2 RECURRING TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES IN MIGRATION WITH A THEMATIC FOCUS

Summer School on Migration Economics

Organisation: Paris School of Economics

Location: Paris, France

Month: June

Website: <https://www.parisschoolofeconomics.eu/en/summer-school/migration-economics/>

Odysseus Summer School on EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy

Organisation: Odysseus Network

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Month: July

Website: <https://odysseus-network.eu/about-the-summer-school/>

International Online School in Forced Migration

Organisation: Refugee Studies Centre, University of Oxford

Location: Oxford, United Kingdom

Month: July

Website: <https://www.rsc.ox.ac.uk/study/international-summer-school>

Summer School on Migration and Human Rights

Organisation: UNICRI

Location: Rome, Italy

Month: July

Website: https://unicri.it/services/education_training/postgraduate

Summer School on European Union Migration Policies

Organisation: Salzburg Centre of European Union Studies (SCEUS)

Location: Salzburg, Austria

Month: July

Website: <https://www.plus.ac.at/news/summer-school-on-european-union-migration-policies-in-july-2025/>

Migration Studies PhD Summer School (MISSCHO)

Organisation: Institute for Migration Research, University of Granada, Spain

Location: Granada, Spain

Month: July

Website: <https://migraciones.ugr.es/formacion/misscho>

Summer School on Migration, Integration and Ethnic Relations (ERCOMER) & The External Dimension of European Union Law

Organisation: Utrecht University

Location: Utrecht, Netherlands

Month: July-August

Website: <https://utrechtsummerschool.nl/>

Summer school courses organised by Radboud University Network on Migrant Inclusion (RUNOMI)

Organisation: Radboud University

Location: Nijmegen, Netherlands

Month: July

Website: <https://www.ru.nl/en/education/more-education-and-training/summer-courses>

Hard-to-Reach: Applied Research Methods with Hidden, Marginal and Excluded Populations

Organisation: Oxford University, Nuffield College

Location: Oxford, UK

Month: August

Website: <https://www.ncrm.ac.uk/training/>

Summer School on the Economics of Migration

Organisation: UC Davis, Global Migration Center

Location: Mexico City, Mexico

Month: September

Website: <https://globalmigration.ucdavis.edu/>

Please note that the exact dates and details for some events may vary annually. It is advisable to check the respective websites for the most current information.

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

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